

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL IDEAS OF O. Y. SAVCHENKO

Shepitko O.

Postgraduate student, Educational and Pedagogical Sciences,

V. O. Sukhomlynskyi Mykolaiv National University,

Research coordinator: Yakymenko S.I., doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, professor,

V.O. Sukhomlynskyi Mykolaiv National University,

м. Mykolaiv

Abstract

The article reveals several significant innovative pedagogical ideas of the famous teacher, didactician and scientist Oleksandra Yakivna Savchenko. It is noted that the scientist focused her attention on the study and research of critical thinking skills of primary school students; indicated the importance of the competence approach as one of the resources for the innovative education development, proving the importance of forming students' key and subject competencies and their impact on learning in general.

Keywords: pedagogical innovation, critical thinking, competence approach.

One of the most important components of society is education. On the one hand, education should quickly and effectively answer the state of scientific and technological progress and trends in the development of the country's economic sphere, and on the other hand, education continues to influence all spheres and processes of social life, as it trains specialists, develops a personality and its life views. Therefore, the current state, problems of implementation and prospects of innovations in education deserve special attention and study.

Today, pedagogical education has set the main goal as qualitative training of teachers who will be competitive and highly qualified in any field of education, able to carry out professional activities based on the principles of democracy, humanism, human focus, free competition and using high technologies, including networking.

It is important to consider teacher education as a means of self-development and self-realization, which changes the goals of education, its motives, forms, methods, and the role of the teacher and lecturer. One of the tasks of modern pedagogical education is to form a person with an innovative type of thinking, an innovative type of pedagogical culture, with a formed alacrity for innovative activity, a specialist capable of meeting all the challenges of civilization, especially in the context of European integration.

Taking into account the peculiarities of innovation policy of highly developed countries, their understanding of the development of this science, in the early 90s of the XX century, Ukraine set a course for innovative development, that was reflected in a number of legislative and regulatory documents, such as the Laws of Ukraine "On Innovative Activity", in the field of education - the laws of Ukraine: "On Education", "On Higher Education" and others [1].

Ukraine's transition to an innovative development scheme has significantly accelerated the process of education reform. The focus of leading educational laws, concepts and doctrines is on a competent, spiritual, competitive personality. Innovative processes are becoming the basis of a new philosophy of education that meets the following requirements: taking into account

the peculiarities of the modern educational process, its content and structure, the cycles of students' life, their abilities, interests and inclinations; focus on modelling the educational environment, its organizational, methodological and content components, taking into account typical and individual differences between students, forms of their manifestation in the field of communication relations and cognitive activity, the experience of students' interaction with the outside world; variability and personality-oriented preference of the educational process, as a result of which the knowledge, students' skills and abilities turn into a means of developing their cognitive and personal qualities, ensure their ability to be a subject of their own development; ensuring a holistic psychological and didactic design of the educational process in the conditions of level and profile differentiation of learning [2].

Nowadays the attention of scientists is focused on finding new directions for a holistic study of the field of education, emphasizing the value bases of its modernization, determining the conditions for the effectiveness of innovation processes in education, ensuring its continuity (V. P. Andrushchenko, L. M. Vashchenko, L. I. Danilenko, I. M. Dychkivska, O. A. Dubaseniuk, I. A. Ziaziun, V. G. Kremen, V. I. Lugovyi, V. O. Ogneviuk, V. F. Palamarchuk, M. M. Potashnyk, O. Y. Savchenko, S. O. Sysoieva, A. Khutorskyi, N. Yusufbekova, and others).

Among the most famous figures of the national pedagogy of primary education in recent decades, a prominent place is occupied by a well-known scientist and didactician, developer of the Primary Education Concept and State Standards, head of the All-Ukrainian Association of V. O. Sukhomlynskyi, author of the model educational program for general secondary education institutions "NUS - 1, 2, 3, 4" O. Y. Savchenko. [3]

According to Oleksandra Yakovlevna, pedagogical innovation is the process of creating, disseminating and using new tools (innovations) to solve pedagogical problems that have been solved in a different way, as well as creating new content, forms and methods of educational activities. Pedagogical innovations are aimed

at positive transformations of pedagogical reality, and presuppose the readiness of teachers to innovate. [4]

The study and synthesis of the scientist's academic achievements indicates the formed platform of the created pedagogical innovations: scientific fundamentality of the new, which is offered to practitioners; comprehensiveness of the testing of the new, which precedes its generalization at the level of scientific publications; giving basic importance to integrative nature in the implementation of child-focus in education through the presentation of each one among the newly created scientific and pedagogical products. This ensures that the pedagogical society is guaranteed a consistently high assessment and factual assimilation of the ideas that make up the scientific and practical achievements of the scientist.

The educational society is widely aware that O. Savchenko proposed the primary education specialists' new forms of work organization, pedagogical innovations management of the processes of creation, development, evaluation, and new technological approaches to ensuring pedagogical interaction of the educational process subjects.

It is appropriate to focus on one of the most powerful ideas inherent in O. Y. Savchenko's didactic system, because its constructiveness is associated with the irreversibility of the reform process - conceptual and normative support for the development of critical thinking of a 6–10-year-old child. [3]

The modern researchers associate the concept of "critical thinking" with the teachings of Socrates and its interpretation, on the one hand, as an analysis of facts to form a judgement, and, on the other hand, the intellectual ability to "judge" and "be able to distinguish" (Alekseeva V. V., Underwood M. K., Wade S., Kvaritiuk N. M., Cooper J. L., et al.) In fact, a person uses critical thinking to improve his or her own thinking, because it involves more active use of logic, diversity of testing of educational information, and awareness of evidence. [2] Instead, it is fundamentally important to develop this type of thinking from the first days of school. This is the basis of O. Savchenko's view on the creation, evaluation, development and use of pedagogical innovations. The comprehensive requirement that the author lays down in the model educational program for general secondary education institutions for the relevant academic disciplines is reflexivity, that is, drawing the attention of students to making decisions that "guide their beliefs and actions", because this creates the opportunity to make "more substantive conclusions" [5]. In addition, the "Model Educational Programs for General Secondary Education Institutions. Primary Education", developed under the head of O. Savchenko, also outlines the indicative parameters of students' educational and cognitive achievements [6]. In this area, the "language inventory" is detailed, which provides (at the level of general and compulsory results) constructive formation of the primary schoolchild's ability to think critically. In addition, the researcher proposes a pedagogical system that includes multidimensional observations, analysis, interpretation, evaluation, inference, and explanation of the decision-making process of primary school children. At the

same time, the basic aspects of critical thinking as a complex phenomenon are taken into account - organizational (ability to extract the necessary information from various sources), operational (skills to perform actions according to an algorithm), informational (ability to use what has been acquired in various fields of activity), communicative (ability to lead a dialogue).

The work of O. Savchenko focuses on constructive pedagogical technologies for improving the skills of critical thinking of the individual - one of the main life competences. And this is only a consideration of one of the ideas of pedagogical innovation proposed by the outstanding teacher. Accordingly, a generalization is made that the teacher of the New Ukrainian School is obliged to show "patient correction", encouraging children to think critically. [3]

The analysis of the competence-based approach as a resource for innovative development of school education by Oleksandra Yakovlevna is noteworthy. According to the educator, competence-based education is a way beyond the traditional learning paradigm. Its integrated result is considered not a system of knowledge, skills and abilities of a student, but the ability to act effectively: competence-based education is personal and effective, shifting the emphasis to the ability of a person to act in a certain context. [7]

As a result of the study, Oleksandra Savchenko concluded that the competence-based approach combines learning and students' development, and allows for the systematic modernization of all educational process components: content, methods, learning environment, learning quality assessment criteria, etc. Implementation of the competence approach promotes a teacher and a student focus on the effective component of learning, increases children's motivation, and creates conditions for mastering learning activities. There is a close relationship between key and subject competences: without subject competences, it is impossible to form high-quality key competences, which, in turn, are the interdisciplinary basis for the interconnected implementation of the teaching goals, upbringing and development of students. [7]

The introduction of innovative technologies into the educational space of Ukraine has been increasing every year and reaching a new level. The educational process in Ukraine has numerous prospects in the field of innovation, and Ukrainian researchers continue to conduct scientific research in this area in order to raise the quality of domestic education to the highest European level, which would meet the advanced standards of educational criteria, especially in the context of European integration.

References

1. <https://enic.in.ua/index.php/ua/systema-osvity/zakonodavstvo-v-sferi-osviti>
2. <https://naurok.com.ua/problemi-vprovadzhenya-pedagogichnih-innovacij-u-navchalno-vihovniy-proces-pochatkovo-shkoli-44072.html>
3. https://undip.org.ua/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Zbirnyk_I_pedchytan_2021.pdf
4. Savchenko O. Y. Didactics of primary education: a textbook. Kyiv: Hramota, 2012. 504 c

5. Bolshakova I. Critical thinking. Primary school. K: First Publishing House.

6. Typical educational programs for general secondary education institutions. Primary education. K: TD "Education - Centre Plus", 2018. 240 c.

7. http://www.irbis-nbu.gov.ua/cgi-bin/irbis_nbu/cgiirbis_64.exe?I21DBN=LINK&P21DBN=UJRN&Z21ID=&S21REF=10&S21CNR=20&S21STN=1&S21FMT=ASP_meta&C21COM=S&2_S21P03=FILA=&2_S21STR=Nvidgu_2015_33_36